

Dual Arrangement, Elastic Scattering-Uniform Distribution Statistical Approaches Applied to the Tsallis Distribution

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We argue that there are two independent statistical approaches to obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution. Both are approximations and these approximations coincide. Furthermore, both are based on physical scenarios, namely a maximum number of arrangements subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = E/E_1$ in a global view and elastic 2-body scattering-uniform distribution $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ ($p(e_i)$ unnormalized) in a local subset $e_i+e_j=E_1$ view. We have noted before that if one considers the latter approach, one may first obtain $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ and then create the math function, $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ (which is called Shannon's entropy) and which, when maximized subject to the global constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = E/E_1$, also yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

At first glance, this might give the impression that the elastic scattering-uniform distribution approach is the fundamental one as Shannon's entropy arises from it. We argue here, however, that Shannon's entropy also follows from an independent global approach of maximizing the number of arrangements, i.e. $N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$, where $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i and N , the total number of particles. Thus, the main point we stress in this note is that there is a dual viewpoint and one should consider both approaches. We apply this reasoning to the derivation of the Tsallis distribution.

We begin with the elastic-uniform distribution approach, but with the parameter q present, $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l = E_1$ does not mean that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ because this would bypass the information contained in q . At best one may say that in the $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1}$, $p_{\text{Tsallis}}(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized. The problem is that there are multiple $p(e_i)$'s which satisfy this condition, namely both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions and there is no way to determine which one is the solution. If, however, one also considers the independent arrangement approach, even though arrangements do not apply to the q case, the arrangement form should appear in the entropy in the $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1}$. This means that one does not have any arbitrary function $F(q, p(e_i))$ (entropy) to maximize subject to the global constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)^q = E/E_1$. In particular, one must have an $F(p(e_i))$ which has the appearance of $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ in the $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1}$. We thus suggest the form $\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(q, p(e_i))$ where $F(q, p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. In such a case, one may see that it is the Tsallis form (i.e. one of the possible solutions of the subset elastic scattering-uniform distribution approach) which satisfies a maximum entropy subject to constraint situation. In other words, the elastic scattering approach yields more than one candidate solution, while the global maximization of a function which becomes the arrangement approximation yields a single solution which matches one of the elastic scattering-uniform distribution results. Nevertheless, we still argue for a dualism because the global approach yields a solution included in possible solutions of the elastic case.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and the Elastic Scattering-Uniform Distribution Approach

Even though one may state a global constraint for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, namely:

Sum over i $e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((1))

one may solve the problem in a subset space $e_i + e_j = E_1$ for elastic scattering. This means that:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ if } e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E_1 \text{ ((2))}$$

((2)) is consistent with $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$ for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized ((3)). This leads to the solution:

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ ((4))}$$

Thus, a subset elastic scattering-uniform distribution approach solves the entire problem with no need for a global approach, namely maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint ((1)). Furthermore, if one wishes to use a global approach, one may create Shannon's entropy from the knowledge of ((4)), namely that:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ for } p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized or } \ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + \text{constant for } p(e_i) \text{ normalized ((5))}$$

Then, if one has a global function $F(p(e_i))$ which needs to be maximized subject to ((1)):

$$dF/dp(e_i) = -C_1 e_i/T \text{ ((6))}$$

$$((6)) \text{ and } ((5)) \text{ yield: } dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant}_1 + \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ ((7))}$$

$$\text{which yields the solution: } F(p(e_i)) = -p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ ((8))}$$

At this point, one might be under the impression that one only needs the subset elastic scattering-uniform distribution approach to solve the problem and that the global approach is not independent. We argue, however, that the global approach is independent and that one has a dual scenario in this statistical case.

Arrangements and Global Independent Approach to Solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Distribution

In the previous section, we argued that one may use a subset $e_i + e_j = E_1$ elastic scattering-uniform distribution approach to find the MB distribution. Furthermore, one can derive Shannon's entropy from this approach. Even though that is the case, one may consider a completely independent global approach to solving the problem, namely maximizing the number of arrangements:

$$N! / \text{Product } n(e_i)! \text{ Subject to the constraint } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \text{ with } n(e_i) = N p(e_i) \text{ ((9))}$$

We note that both approaches are based on strictly physical considerations. We also point out that ((9)) differs from the subset elastic scattering uniform distribution approach unless one makes the following approximation:

$$\ln(n(e_i)!) = n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad \text{Stirling's approximation ((10))}$$

Both approaches yield the same result if one ensures that both treat approximations in the same manner. We note that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ involves approximations because for E_{total} , $e_i = .7 E_{\text{total}}$ and $e_j = .8 E_{\text{total}}$ lead to $p(1.5 E_{\text{total}})$, but such a probability should not exist, but it does for $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Dualism

We suggest that there exists a global (entropy maximization) local (subset elastic scattering uniform distribution) dualism. Both represent independent physical ways of solving the problem and both should be taken seriously.

Tsallis Case and the Subset Elastic Scattering -Uniform Distribution Approach

We define a Tsallis scenario as one with a global constraint:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) e_i^q = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((11))$$

Thus, an independent parameter q appears. This means that even for the subset:

$$e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E_1 \quad ((12))$$

one can no longer state that: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((13))

To do so would bypass the implications of q . One does know, however, that for

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((14))$$

The problem is that ((14)) does not lead to a unique solution. First of all, one cannot consider $qC \exp(-e_i/T)$ or $C \exp(-qe_i/T)$ as solutions which yield the MB case for $q=1$. We suggest that this means that one considers a finite power series in e_i/T . The two simplest cases are:

$$p(e_i) = (1 + (1-q)x)^{-1/(1-q)} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((15a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$p(e_i) = (\sqrt{1 + (1-q)(1-q)xx} + (1-q)x)^{-1/(1-q)} \quad ((15b))$$

The first is the Tsallis solution and the second, the Kaniadakis, but at this point both are potential math solutions and one cannot pick one or the other. The subset elastic scattering

approach does not yield a unique solution, although one of the solutions (or another if it exists) must hold.

Tsallis Distribution and a Global Approach

We now consider the independent global approach. Even though one can no longer consider maximizing arrangements because of q , in the $\lim q \rightarrow 1$ one must obtain the Stirling approximation form

$$\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((16))$$

We suggest for the global case:

$\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(q, p(e_i))$ ((17a)) such that $F(q, p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((17b)) as in the MB case, and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} F(q, p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((17c))$$

We note that the form $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + \text{constant}$ in the MB case holds for both the local and global approaches.

((17)) suggests that: $p(e_i)^q dF/dp = \text{constant}$ which take to be 1. Then:

$$F(q, p(e_i)) = -\{1 - p(e_i)^{1-q}\} / (1-q) \quad ((18))$$

((18)) is a unique solution and one may see that the first solution ((15a)) from the subset elastic scattering approach satisfies ((17b)).

Thus, it is not sufficient to solve the Tsallis problem by simply using one approach, namely the local elastic scattering-uniform distribution one, but should consider both the global and local approaches. The global approach actually yields a unique solution by itself, but it is linked to a possible solution of the local approach. Thus, we argue that a dual physical scenario exists.

Conclusion

We suggest that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann and also the Tsallis case that a dual physical-statistical scenario exists. The MB case may be solved by considering a local approach, based on physical elastic 2-body scattering. This is local because one uses a subset $e_i + e_j = E_1$ and the notion of uniform distribution because for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E_1$, $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ leading to the notion of $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. From this, one can actually create a math function $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ which when maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, also yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

At this point, one might think that all that one needs is the local approach. We argue here, however, that this is not the case. We suggest that there exists an independent global physical scenario based on the maximization (in the MB case) of the number of arrangements: $N!$

Product over i $n(e_i)!$ (where $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$) subject to the constraint Sum over i $e_i p(e_i)$. There is no need for any notion of the elastic scattering approach to solve the global problem, but it is only when one uses the approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ (i.e. Stirling's approximation) that the two approaches coincide. It is the approximation which yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ which is observed in nature. We thus argue for a statistical-physical dualism. There is both an independent physical global approach (arrangements) and a local (elastic scattering) independent approach.

We apply the idea of this dualism to the Tsallis case for which one has the constraint Sum over i $e_i p(e_i)^q$. The presence of q means that for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E$, one no longer has $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$. In the limit $q \rightarrow 1$, however, $p(e_i) \rightarrow C \exp(-e_i/T)$. We suggest that this leads to at least two math solutions ((15a)) and ((15b)) and that one does not know which one to choose. Using the global approach, even though the arrangements approach no longer holds for $q \neq 1$, in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$, one should obtain the arrangements form. We thus suggest a function Sum over i $p(e_i)^q$ $F(q, p(e_i))$ such that $F(q, p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and that for $q \rightarrow 1$ $F(q, p(e_i)) \rightarrow \ln(p(e_i))$. This then leads to the unique solution $F(q, p(e)) = -(1 + p(e)^q)^{1/(1-q)}$. We note that the first $p(e_i)$ possible solution from the elastic scattering approach ((15a)) leads to $F(q, p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and so this is the solution. Thus, we argue that dualism of approaches exists, both physical and one global and the other local.